

ANALYTICAL METHOD OF DETERMINATION OF LEAGUE GROUPING AND LEAF COVER COVERING IN CHEMICAL PROCESSING BETWEEN COTTON ROWS

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ABSTRACT

This article presents research work related to the installation of spraying structures on cultivators of the KHU-4 brand during the chimes processing of cotton.

The use of machinery and technical equipment in the development of agriculture remains one of the factors that ensure the quality of work in agriculture in a short time on the basis of agro-technical requirements and increase labor productivity.

One of the urgent tasks is to increase the productivity of the unit and the yield of cotton by creating a combined machine-tractor unit, especially when working with a cultivator type KXU-4.

The proposed combined unit effectively combats various diseases and pests with a high degree of "coverage" by using

chemical pesticides on the surface of the cotton body and leaves in a single pass.

The combined KXU-4 cultivator is equipped with a fan sprayer, which allows spraying of a chemical pesticide suspension on the surface of the cotton body and leaves with a high degree of "coverage" on the cotton body and the lower and upper surfaces of the leaves.

However, it is necessary to study the degree of flexibility of this combined structure to the cotton plant depending on the growing seasons. In order to determine such flexibility on the basis of scientific research, experiments were conducted in

2021 on cotton fields planted on a 90 x 90 scheme. The experiments were carried out at the Samarkand Institute of Veterinary Medicine at the State Unitary Enterprise for Training and Experimental Farms in Aqdarya district and at the Abdullo farm in Pastdargom district, on the cotton fields named after Omad.

During the experiments, the length of the cotton body and the surface of the leaves (branching, height, body

thickness, etc.) were measured with a tape measure, surface analytic detector (planimeter) and other measuring instruments, with sufficient number of turns." Was calculated and calculated.

The surface dimensions of cotton leaves were divided into three groups, namely - large, medium and small, the classification of groups on the measurement of leaf surfaces is shown in Figure 1.

Figure-1. Classification of cotton garden surfaces: a) large b) medium and c) small leafy surfaces.

Each field experiment was repeated with an accuracy of 3 to 20 times. Measurements were determined by multiplying the number of cotton buds on

the surface of a single area and the average number of leaves per cotton plant. Sample leaves were taken from the lower, middle and upper parts of the cotton and their total surfaces were calculated using the following formula:

$$\Sigma S_{bsm} = \Sigma S_{laef} + \Sigma S_{b.surface} + \Sigma S_{b.common,surface} \cdot m^2 \quad (1)$$

Where, ΣS_{laef} - total surface area of biological mass in cotton, m^2 ;

$\Sigma S_{b.surface}$ - General of large, medium and small leaves of cotton surface, m^2 ;

$\Sigma S_{b.common,surface}$ - General during the growing season of the body of the cotton surface, m^2 .

The total surface area of the large, medium, and small leaves of the cotton given in Equation (1) above was determined by the following equation:

$$\Sigma S_{b.surface} = S_{big.laef} \cdot n + S_{medium.laf} \cdot n + S_{small.laef} \cdot n \quad (2)$$

$\Sigma S_{b.surface}$ - surface area of large leaves of cotton, m²;

$S_{big.laef}$ - surface of middle leaves in cotton, m²;

$S_{small.laef}$ - surface area of small leaves in cotton, m²;

n- the number of large, medium, and small leaf clusters in the cotton.

The total surface area of biomass in cotton (ΣS_{laef}) Depending on the presence of several rows of cotton in one row (2 rows, row spacing 90 cm), it is determined by the following equation:

$$\Sigma S_{laef} = (S_{big.laef} + S_{medium.laef} + S_{small.laef}) \cdot n \quad (3)$$

On the basis of the fan spraying device mounted on the cultivator KXU-4, we find the total surface area of cotton leaves (ΣS_{cover}) by the following equation:

$$\Sigma S_{cover} = \pi \cdot l_{cover} \cdot (r_1 + r_2) \cdot n \quad (4)$$

In this case, ΣS_{cover} - length of cotton field, m; r_1 and r_2 -- the radius of covering the cotton with the chemical working mixture on the rods in the first (leaf surface to the top) and the second (leaf surface to the tag side), m. We define the total biological mass surface area per hectare of cotton as follows:

$$\Sigma S_{bms / hectare} = \Sigma S_{bms} \cdot n_{cottona / hectare}, m^2$$

In this case, $n_{cottona / hectare}$, - number of cotton stalks per hectare,

Analytical studies show that the process of cultivating cotton rows with a cultivator KXU-4 can be used to control various plant diseases and pests by spraying a chemical mixture on the cotton body and leaves.

In this analytical process, the order of grouping of the cotton body and its leaves was formed, an analytical method was developed to spray the chemical suspension on the surface of the lower and upper parts of the leaves in each group and determine how much the leaf surface was covered with the working mixture.

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